

ARGO GENERATION BASED ON EXTERNAL SOURCE

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Abstract: The formation of slang based on an external source is different from the system in literary language. Borrowed slangs are not used to name the lacunae in the language, to name the words in the action (theft process), but for innovation and emphasis.

Key words and phrases: slang, lacuna, borrowed words, innovation, acquisition of another language.

The creation of an argo based on an external source is different from the system in a literary language. Here: 1) a word is taken from a foreign language - it has a dictionary and slang meaning; 2) the meaning of slang in a foreign language is slightly changed, and thus it is adopted into another language.

Borrowed slangs are not used to name the lacunae in the language, to name the words in the action (theft process), but for innovation and emphasis. —It is known that when borrowed words retain their dictionary meaning (if it is a polysemous word, one meaning) when transferred to another language, only 30% of the borrowed words in the criminal world remain in their meaning, and the remaining 70% are used in a completely different sense[1]:
- Everyone here considers himself a passenger. (Passenger is a person who was caught by accident. - From the author's comment).

(Murdalar gapirmaydilar, p. 5)

The Russian word passenger means passenger, but as a Russian slang —1) epzyz; 2) a person who has suffered injustice; 3) refers to such notions as a cheated gambler[2] and refers to a person who has been unjustly imprisoned by accident.

- You like to sell yours. «козёл» also comes out of you more. Is there no other state farm director like you? But bribery is everywhere.

(Murdalar gapirmaydilar, p. 14)

Although the word “Козёл” means goat in Russian, it is used slang for an active helper of the prison administration, and it also has the same meaning in Uzbek.

They have no interest in blackness. (Samum, p. 213)

“Чернота” means black, darkness, abyss[3] in Russian, and refers to black medicine in Uzbek. At this point, it should be mentioned that the semantic meaning of the derived words in the literary language is —inviolable remains and enters another language as a unit representing the crime lexicon.

The meaning of slang in a foreign language has changed a little and will be assimilated into another language without any changes. Although it does not mean anything in the literary language of a given language, it expresses a concept as slang:

Your skin is still red because of serving the cops.

(Shaytanat, Book 1. p. 170)

Usually, the word – “мент” is considered a Russian slang, and currently it does not have a dictionary meaning.

However, –... in ancient times was derived from the word –mentor, and it meant tutor, teacher[4], it does not have a dictionary meaning, that is, it has a form: although it does not have a standard form, it means the following meanings as a substandard: –1) a post holder; 2) Izquvar; 3) supervisor; 4) policeman; 5) as a law enforcement officer[5]. This slang in the Russian language also expresses the above meanings in the speech of Uzbek thieves and thieves.

It should be mentioned here that a large part of Uzbek slang is Russian slang. The reason for this is that our country was colonized by this country in the past, and as a result of many people of different nationalities immigrating and settling there, the phenomenon of language elements took place. In addition, in the last century, all administration, especially the criminal system, was carried out in Russian, so we can find Russian slangs in the speech of this world. In addition, we can see that such a phenomenon is observed in almost all languages: 12% of Gypsy to Russian, 35% to English; 17 percent of words from Arabic have been adopted into French as slang [1].

As V. A. Khomyakov very reasonably pointed out, in the system of argo, borrowing a foreign word occupies a very important place [6]. Indeed, at the expense of adopted argos, the productivity of substandards increases, which, in turn, creates the basis for the creation of new subcodes in a given language.

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